

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING SPEAKING FLUENCY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

Nabiyeva Xilola Abdulmuratovna

Senior teacher, UzSWLU

Sa'dullayeva Madinabonu

Student, UzSWLU

Annotation: *This article discusses the importance of digital technologies in improving students' speaking fluency in English language learning. Many learners face difficulties in speaking due to lack of confidence and limited vocabulary. The study focuses on the use of modern digital tools such as mobile applications and online platforms in language teaching. The research was conducted among 32 students using questionnaires, pre-test and post-test, and interviews. The results show that digital technologies help students speak more fluently, use a wider range of vocabulary, and express their ideas more clearly. The article concludes that integrating digital tools into language teaching can significantly enhance students' speaking skills.*

Key words: *Digital technologies, speaking fluency, English language teaching, mobile applications, online platforms, artificial intelligence, language learning, communication skills, EFL learners, digital tools*

Introduction

Nowadays our world is developing day – by – day, and this is effecting how we are teaching students and how we learning languages. In modern education, digital technologies play a very important role in teaching and learning language. Most of language learners are face with problems in speaking fluency. They often feel shy, lack vocabulary, and can not express their ideas in another language appropriately. Traditional teaching methods are sometimes not enough to solve this problem. Therefore, using digital technologies can be an effective solution to improve students' speaking skill. During this article, we are going to discuss about that problem and its up-to-date solutions.

In recent years, the integration of technology into education has created new opportunities for language learning. Mobile applications, online platforms, and artificial intelligence tools provide learners with interactive and flexible environments where they can practice speaking more frequently. These tools also allow students to receive instant feedback, which helps them correct their mistakes and improve their confidence.

This article aims to explore the role of digital technologies in enhancing students' speaking fluency in English language teaching. It also discusses the main challenges learners face and provides possible solutions based on modern technological approaches.

Literature review

Many researchers have studied the role of digital technologies in language learning. In recent years, technology has become an important part of education because it helps students learn in a more interesting and effective way. Chapelle (2003) explains that technology gives learners more opportunities to practice language skills in real communication situations. It also helps teachers create interactive activities that support student learning.

Kukulka-Hulme (2020) highlights that mobile-assisted language learning is very useful for students. Mobile applications allow learners to study English anytime and anywhere. This means students are not limited to classroom time only. They can practice speaking, listening, and vocabulary through different apps, which makes learning more flexible and continuous.

Li (2022) also states that artificial intelligence tools are becoming very popular in education. AI-based systems can give students instant feedback on their speaking performance. For example, they can help learners with pronunciation, grammar mistakes, and fluency problems. This kind of feedback helps students improve faster and become more confident in speaking English.

In addition, other studies show that digital technologies increase students' motivation and interest in learning English. When students use online platforms or mobile applications, they feel more comfortable and less stressed. They are also more willing to participate in speaking activities because technology creates a friendly and supportive learning environment.

Overall, previous research shows that digital technologies play an important role in improving speaking fluency. They provide more practice opportunities, immediate feedback, and a more engaging learning experience for students.

Methodology

This study was conducted to investigate the role of artificial intelligence in improving students' speaking fluency in English language learning. The research was carried out with 32 English language learners. In this study, a mixed-method approach was used. Three main methods were applied: questionnaire, speaking test (pre-test and post-test), and classroom observation. These methods helped to collect different types of data about students' speaking skills and their use of AI tools.

1. Questionnaire

A questionnaire was used as the first method. It was given to 32 students. The questionnaire included simple questions about students' experience with artificial intelligence tools in English learning. Students were asked how often they use AI tools, what they think about these tools, and whether they believe these tools help improve their speaking skills. This method helped to understand students' general opinions and attitudes toward using AI in language learning.

2. Speaking Test (Pre-test and Post-test)

The second method was a speaking test. At the beginning of the study, a pre-test was given to students to check their speaking level. In this test, students spoke on simple topics to show their initial fluency, vocabulary use, and confidence. After that, students practiced speaking using artificial intelligence tools during the learning process. These tools helped students to practice speaking more often and improve their language skills. At the end of the study, a post-test was conducted using similar speaking tasks. The results of the pre-test and post-test were compared to see the improvement in students' speaking fluency, vocabulary, and confidence.

3. Classroom Observation

The third method was classroom observation. The researcher observed students during speaking lessons where artificial intelligence tools were used. The observation focused on students' participation, their use of AI tools, and their confidence while speaking English. It also helped to see how students behaved during speaking activities

and how they reacted when using technology in the classroom. This method provided real and practical information about students' learning process.

The results of this study show that artificial intelligence helps students improve their speaking fluency in English. The study was done with 32 students. Different methods such as a pre-test, a post-test, a questionnaire, and classroom observation were used to get the results.

At the beginning of the study, in the pre-test, most students had problems with speaking English. They could not speak fluently. They often stopped when speaking because they forgot words. Many students also felt shy and nervous. Their speaking level was not high, and they needed more practice.

After that, students used artificial intelligence tools to practice speaking English. These tools helped students to learn new words and practice speaking more often. Students could repeat words many times and practice pronunciation. They also felt more comfortable when speaking English with the help of technology.

In the post-test, the results showed improvement. Students spoke better than before. They used more words and made fewer mistakes. They also spoke with more confidence. Most students could express their ideas more easily after using AI tools.

In addition, during classroom lessons in school, the researcher observed students' speaking activities. When AI tools were used in class, students were more active. They tried to speak more English and participated in speaking tasks. Their speaking performance improved by about 7% compared to the beginning of the study.

The questionnaire also showed positive results. Most students said that AI tools helped them practice English speaking. They said that learning became easier and more interesting. They also said that they were not afraid of speaking English anymore.

Overall, the results show that artificial intelligence is helpful for improving students' speaking fluency. It helps students speak better, feel more confident, and learn English in a better way.

Results and Discussion

This study shows that artificial intelligence is very helpful in improving students' speaking fluency in English language learning. The research was done with 32 students using different methods such as pre-test, post-test, questionnaire, and classroom observation.

The results show that students had many problems in speaking English at the beginning. They were shy, had low vocabulary, and made many pauses. After using AI tools, students improved their speaking skills. They became more confident, used more words, and spoke more fluently.

The classroom observation also showed positive changes. Students were more active and interested in speaking activities. Their speaking performance improved by about 7% after using AI tools in lessons.

In conclusion, artificial intelligence helps students improve their speaking fluency. It makes learning easier, more interesting, and more effective. Teachers can use AI tools in English lessons to help students practice speaking more and improve their skills.

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